

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

Wind

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

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Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.1, Product: Wind
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1 INTRODUCTION

This section focuses on ABL wind profiling presenting an overview of the product capabilities (accuracy, uncertainty estimates, readiness for operation etc...). Existing processing chains are also reported and published references are listed so that the reader can get more details on specific aspects if necessary.

Through all the documents the following acronyms are used:

- ALC: Automatic Lidar Ceilometer
- DL: Doppler Lidar
- MWR: MicroWave Radiometer
- DIAL: Differential Absorption Lidar
- CR, DCR: Cloud Radar, Doppler Cloud Radar
- RL: Raman Lidar
- DeL: Depolarization Lidar
- BL: Backscatter lidar
- RWP: Radar Wind Profilers
- ABL: Atmospheric Boundary Layer

2 METHODS OVERVIEW

Doppler lidar measures the radial Doppler velocity of the backscattered signal. Commercial systems typically operate at infra-red wavelengths close to 1.5 or 2 μm and use heterodyne (coherent) detection to determine the Doppler velocity. Ground-based 'long-range' Doppler lidars are capable of deriving radial velocities and higher moments for turbulent properties with high spatial and temporal resolution. Vertical winds are obtained directly using operation at vertical, whereas the vertical profile of horizontal winds must be derived from a set of scans. Possible scan patterns are Doppler beam swinging (DBS), which comprise a set of 3-5 scans in at least 3 orthogonal directions, and for instruments with hemispherical scanning capability, Velocity Azimuth Display (VAD), which is a conical scan in azimuth at a constant elevation. This scan may contain any number of beams, and is also referred to as a Plan-Position-Indicator (PPI) scan if performed at elevation angles close to horizontal. Turbulent properties can be derived from both vertical and scanning operation.

Other instruments capable of providing profiles of horizontal winds in the ABL include sodars, radar wind profilers (RWP), typically operating at lower frequencies than weather radar, and weather radar. Most RWP use a 4 or 5-beam DBS approach and can obtain winds both in clear air and in cloud/precipitation. Weather radars use VAD or VVP (volume velocity processing¹), with winds being retrieved in the presence of sufficient cloud or precipitation throughout the extent of the scan. The operational weather radar scan schedule may only contain a few low-elevation angle scans.

Scintillometers can also provide information on turbulent parameters such as structure functions and fluxes in the ABL.

Available networks: EPROFILE, ARM, ACTRIS-CLOUDNET (future)

3 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

Products	Radial winds	Mean horizontal winds	Vertical winds	Turbulent properties
Instruments	- DL - DCR	- DL - scanning DCR	- DL - DCR	- DL - DCR
Accuracy requirements	- Not defined	OSCAR-database breakthrough/goal req (for High Resolution Modelling): 1 m.s-1 / 2 m.s-1	OSCAR-database breakthrough/goal req (for High Resolution Modelling) : 1 cm.s-1 / 2 cm.s-1	- Not yet defined
Temporal resolution Requirements	- Not defined	OSCAR-database breakthrough/goal req. (for High Resolution Modelling) : 15min / 60 min	OSCAR-database breakthrough/goal req. (for High Resolution Modelling): 15min / 60 min	- Not yet defined
Assumptions needed	None for radial winds. Pointing accuracy	Assumption of homogeneity	None, if direct measurement (vertical stare) Reconstruct from VAD.	Stationarity assumption and measurement of inertial scales (Kolmogorov)
Existing algorithms	Uncertainty calculation and background correction ^{2,3,4}	DBS ⁵ VAD ^{6,7,8} DVAD ⁹ (Distance Velocity–Azimuth Display) virtual tower ^{10,11,12}	Direct measurement (screening of precipitation required)	Vertical ¹³ Scanning ^{14,15} 6-beam ¹⁶ RHI + vertical ¹⁷
Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Assimilation - Evaluation and verification in Numerical Weather Prediction, climate and air quality models. - Wind energy - Process studies 			
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific community, - Atmospheric modelling (NWP, Climate, Air Quality) - E-PROFILE - National Weather Services - Aviation - Wind energy 			
Readiness for operation	Y	Y	Y	Y
Expected accuracy	Depends on SNR			

Uncertainty estimates existing?	Y	Y	Y	Y
Temporal resolution	< 30 s (usually < 2 s)	< 15 mins (depends on scan schedule - individual scan takes < 2 min)	Usually < 30 s	30 s (3 min for some properties)
Timeliness	Real-time (< 5 min)	Real-time (< 5 min)	Immediately	Currently 1 day (requires extensive processing)
Data availability	24/7 although data availability also depends on SNR			
Data format	netCDF			

Products	Wind gusts	Alerts
Instruments	- DL	- DL - DCR
Accuracy requirements	- OSCAR-database breakthrough/goal req (for Nowcasting): 1 m.s-1 / 1.7 m.s-1	- Not yet defined
Temporal resolution Requirements	- OSCAR-database breakthrough/goal req (for Nowcasting): - 60 sec. / 10 minutes	- Not yet defined
Assumptions needed	Ability to upscale observed frequency to 'standard' meteorological definition	None
Existing algorithms	Suomi et al. ¹⁸	In development
Applications	Nowcasting and forecasting	
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Weather Services - Aviation - Wind energy 	
Readiness for operation	N	N
Expected accuracy	Depends on SNR	
Uncertainty estimates existing?	N	N
Temporal	10 min	Same as horizontal winds

resolution		
Timeliness	10 min	< 5 min
Data availability	24/7 although data availability also depends on SNR	
Data format	netCDF	

4 REFERENCES

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Note that there are many more algorithms for deriving winds and turbulent properties, some of which include additional instrumentation.